

BILINGUALISM AND IDENTITY: THE PRACTICE OF SELF-TRANSLATION AMONG ROMANIAN AUTHORS

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This research explores the complex interplay between bilingualism, identity and literary creation, focusing on the practice of self-translation among Romanian and Moldovan authors. It delves into the historical roots of linguistic diversity in the region, examines prominent literary figures who navigated multiple languages, and analyzes the unique challenges and opportunities presented by self-translation as a creative act. At first glance, self-translation may appear to be an ideal solution to many of the challenges posed by literary translation. However, a closer examination reveals that self-translation is a far more complex and demanding process than it initially seems. It requires not only a deep mastery of both languages but also the ability to recreate literary style, tone and cultural context without compromising artistic integrity. Due to these high demands and the pressure to meet rigorous literary standards in more than one language, self-translation remains a rare and exceptional practice in the literary world.